

BIODIVERSITY AND GUILD STRUCTURE OF SPIDERS (ARACHNIDA: ARANEA) FROM BANANA PLANTATION OF DISTRICT MATIARI, SINDH, PAKISTAN

SHADAB KAKA

Department of Zoology, University of Sindh, Jamshoro.

TAHIRA JABEEN URSANI

Department of Zoology, University of Sindh, Jamshoro.

SAMINA MALIK *

Department of Zoology, University of Sindh, Jamshoro.

*Corresponding Author Email: seemimalik68@gmail.com

Abstract

Biodiversity of spiders was measured very rich in the District Matiari; due to its favorite climatic and abiotic (temperature and humidity) conditions. While second parameter, the ecological guild concept has been of great interest to persons (arachnologists, farmers, landlords and natives engaged with integrated pest managements) and the different manner in which spiders' exploration for common resource-prey arthropods has led to numerous attempts to classify them into guilds. Though, questions have been raised about the validity of guilds and the taxon-centered basis of their definition. Here, we propose an alternative approach to guild classification, using quantitative analysis of ecological characteristics of spider families with special reference of this proposal studies. During this study six families are identified namely; Araneidae, Lycosidae, Oxyopidae, Tetragnathidae, Salticidae and Gnaphosidae. These families were classified on the basis of their web-building and predation methods.

Keywords: Biodiversity; Guild Structure; Spiders; Banana; Matiari; Hyderabad; Sindh.

INTRODUCTION

Pakistan is rich in spider fauna and has diverse habitats [1,2] Spiders are ancient and successful group of invertebrates and known as poisonous arthropods [3, 10,11]. This quality makes them the most suitable potential bio-control agents for regulating the population of insect pests in different agro-ecosystems and requires their extensive study. Spiders are one the most important group of biological predators in nature. They are eight legged Arthropods and largest order Araneae of the Class Arachnida. They are ranked at the seventh number in the biodiversity [12]. Throughout in the world as by the August 2022, 50,356 species of spiders have been identified with 132 families and many archeologists' works on the diverse aspects of spiders [13-24]. Banana (*Musa paradidica*L.) plant has been fit in to family Musaceae, it is major fruit grown in Sindh, Pakistan. All the abiotic and climatic conditions favor the growth of banana crops in the Sindh. Hence it is cultivated in thousands of hectares. Banana crops are infected by the numbers of the pests, such as banana aphids, weevils, coconut scale, thrips and Nematodes. The farmer of Sindh, Pakistan generally uses chemical pesticides to protect their crops which have many hazardous affects on the climate as well as on man [25-27].

For the chemicals, the best alternate is the biological control, which refers to the use of natural enemies against the pest population to reduce the pest's density. It is one of the safe methods to control the pests because it is not toxic, pathogenic and injurious to human beings. Biological control has the advantage of being self-established and usually does not harm non-targeted organisms in the environment. It is regarded as safe and never polluting, nor does it leave residues on food, a concern to many people today.

Recent many developments have been preceded in favor of bio control as spiders are the potential biological control agents. Most of spiders are generalist predators. They were not historically considered useful bio-control agents against agricultural pests, because they feed both on harmful as well as beneficial insects. However, studies have indicated that spiders can help suppress pest populations. Spiders are abundant and widespread in almost all ecosystems and constitute one of the most important components of global biodiversity. Spiders have a very significant role to play in ecology by being exclusively predatory and thereby maintaining ecological equilibrium. It is estimated that the world's 25 million tons of spiders kill 400–800 million tons of prey per year.

Most of the spiders are generalist predators feed mainly on phytophagous as well as predaceous insects. Being predatory in nature spiders are very important for the studies concerning the biological control. Only Samina Malik which pioneer description on guild structure from sugar-cane crop present. Information available about the species of spider's guild structure and biodiversity in Pakistan and their distribution are scientifically quite limited as compared to the world knowledge. Biology, ecology, taxonomy, diversity of spiders and guild structure of spiders found in banana crops are particularly limited.

No proper and detailed research work has been done on the biodiversity and Guild structure of spiders from different localities of districts Hyderabad, Shaheed Benazir Abad, Mirpurkhas and Matiyari. Only special reference S. Malik given detail of guild structure of spider from district Tando Jam and sugar crops from Matiyari. It is aimed to this study to present and detail guild structure from another crop of banana from selected areas of Sindh. Present study will provide baseline data about the Banana spider fauna of district Matiyari, which will be helpful to establish and evaluate the future management practices for banana crops as well as any another field.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

For this research the data was planned from the banana fields of District Matiyari located (026°28'13.3"N and 83°38'28.3"E) (**Fig.1**). During field survey from frequently banana growing taulka's (Hala, New Saeedabad and Matiyari), **950 specimen** (including spiderlings) were gathered. The period of this research was from the month of January to October 2021 and January to May 2022. Keys followed; for the identifications of spiders were given by [1,2,3,4], for the study of diversity of spiders methods of [5,6] was applied, and for the revision of guild structure in spiders, producers of [7,8] pursued. All specimens brought to laboratory and sorted out into six families after identification and noted out which family which occupancies nature of living and adopted architect their web and non-

web builders. In this survey three major spider guilds studied from banana crops, Orb-web weavers (Araneidae, Tetragnathidae), Foliage Runners (Gnaphosidae, Oxyopidae) and Ambushes and stalkers (Salticidae, and Lycosidae, Salticidae(**Fig.2-12**).

5

6

7

8

9

10

Figure1: the map of Sindh, showing in the centrally located District Matiari highlighted in yellow color. **Figure2-4,7:** different sites in the banana plantation; showing the pitfall trap method for the collection of spiders. **Figure: 6,8,10** are the some newly reported spider species. **Figure:11,12** in the year 2022, heavy flood came in Sindh and 90-95% banana fields went under water, hence minimum collection was made

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data showed the banana fields of District Matiari are rich in spider fauna (**Fig.13 & table. 2**). **Total 950** specimens were collected. During field survey it was measured that the female spider ratio was too much high than males (10.72% male & female 89.27%).

In this survey three major spider guilds studied from banana crops, Orb-web weavers (Araneidae, Tetragnathidae), Foliage Runners (Gnaphosidae, Oxyopidae) and Ambushes and stalkers (Salticidae, and Lycosidae, Salticidae, their diagnostic characters given in the (**table.1**) and their feeding or guild given in circadian behavior (**Fig.14**).

Table1: families, their Identification keys *I.K and familiar characteristics.

<p>Araneidae(Stalkers & Orb weavers) *I.K: 8 similar eyes; spiny, long legs; with 3 claws; chelicerae not strong; femur IV provided with a double fringe of hairs on the prolateral surface; vertical orb-web builders Fig. a</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">a</p>
<p>Lycosidae (wolf spiders & ground runners) Resemble nursery web spiders and do not spin webs; 8 eyes arranged in three rows; The middle row has 2 very large eyes. Some members of this make deep tubular burrows. Fig. b</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">b</p>

<p>Oxyopidae(lynx spiders) Make little use of webs; have large spiny bristles on their legs Small to medium in body size, 8 eyes, six of them are arranged in hexagonal pattern, other two eyes are smaller; basal part of chelicerae of most oxyopids is large, vertical and parallel; chelicerae with single tooth. Fig. c</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">c</p>
<p>Teteragnathidae(Orb weavers& long jawed); legs and chelicerae elongated; endites elongated and widest at distal edge; Legs very long; Homogenous eyes. Fig. d</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">d</p>
<p>Salticidae(jumping spider); have some of the best vision among arthropods and use it in courtship, hunting, and navigation; known by four pairs of eyes pattern. Fig. e</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">e</p>

Figure 13: diversity and abundance % of the families of spiders recorded from Matiari

Table 2: Numbers of Specimen Collected and Their % From Banana Fields

<i>Taluka</i>	<i>Male</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
<i>Matiyari</i>	45	393	438	46.10%
<i>Hala</i>	33	295	328	34.50%
<i>New Saeedabad</i>	22	162	184	19.40%
<i>Total</i>	100	850	950	100%

Figure 14: Circadian Behaviors, Which Clearly Shown Assemblages with Each Other

References

- 1) Ursani, T.J., Soomro, A.R., Dhilloo, K.H., Soomro, N.M. and Solangi, A.W., 2013. ArgiopeBilali, A New Species of (Araneidae, Arachnida) Bugs Form District Dadu, Sindh.
- 2) Soomro, A.R., Ursani, T.J., Dhilloo, K.H., Malik, S., Khokhar, J.A. And Chandio, J.I., Description of newly identified spider Eusparassusnaheedae (Family: Sparassidae; Order: Araneae) on rice crop at K. N Shah District Dadu, Sindh-Pakistan.
- 3) Coddington, J.A., 2005. Phylogeny and classification of spiders. *Spiders of North America: an identification manual*.
- 4) Maddison, W.P., 2015. A phylogenetic classification of jumping spiders (Araneae: Salticidae). *Journal of Arachnology*, pp.231-292.
- 5) Russell-Smith, A. and Stork, N.E., 1994. Abundance and diversity of spiders from the canopy of tropical rainforests with particular reference to Sulawesi, Indonesia. *Journal of Tropical Ecology*, 10(4), pp.545-558.
- 6) Marusik, Y.M. and Koponen, S., 2002. Diversity of spiders in boreal and arctic zones. *The Journal of Arachnology*, 30(2), pp.205-210.

- 7) Uetz, G.W., Halaj, J. and Cady, A.B., 1999. Guild structure of spiders in major crops. *Journal of Arachnology*, pp.270-280.
- 8) Malik, S., Ursani, T.J., Khokhar, J.A. and Soomro, A.R., 2018. Spider guilds in the sugarcane fields of two districts of Sindh, Pakistan. *Int J Zool*, 3, pp.8-11.
- 9) Malik, S., Ursani, T.J., Soomro, N.M., Narejo, N.T., Khokhar, J.A. and Soomro, A., 2022. Feeding and circadian behaviour of spiders (Aranae: Arachnida) in the sugarcane fields of Matiari and Hyderabad Districts, Sindh. *Journal of Innovative Sciences*, 8(1), pp.75-79.
- 10) Butt, A. and M. A. Beg. 2000. Some new species of Marpissa (Salticidae) from Pakistan. *Pak. J. Zool.*, 32: 75-79.
- 11) Butt, A. and M. A. Beg. 2001. Description of two new species of spiders of the families Clubionidae and Oxyopidae from Pakistan. *Pak. J. Zool.*, 33: 35-37.
- 12) Riechert, S.E. and Lockley, T., 1984. Spiders as biological control agents. *Annual review of entomology*, 29(1), pp.299-320.
- 13) Ndava, J., Llera, S.D. and Manyanga, P., 2018. The future of mosquito control: The role of spiders as biological control agents: A review. *International journal of Mosquito research*, 5(1), pp.6-11.
- 14) Michalko, R., Pekár, S. and Entling, M.H., 2019. An updated perspective on spiders as generalist predators in biological control. *Oecologia*, 189, pp.21-36.
- 15) Hodge, M.A., 1999. The implications of intraguild predation for the role of spiders in biological control. *Journal of Arachnology*, pp.351-362.
- 16) Tikader, B. K. 1982. The Fauna of India: Araneae: Araneidae. *Zool. Surv. India*, 2: 1-293.
- 17) Biswas, B. and K. Biswas. 2003. Fauna of Sikkim (Araneae: Spiders), State Fauna Series, 9:67-100.
- 18) Sunderland, K. (1999). Mechanisms Underlying the Effects of Spiders on Pest Populations. *The Journal of Arachnology*, 27(1), 308–316.
- 19) Yin, C. M., J. F. Wang, M.S. Zhu, L. P. Xie, X. J. Peng and Y. H. Bao. 1997. *Fauna Sinica: Arachnida: Araneae: Araneidae*. Science Press, Beijing, China, : 1-460.
- 20) Yoshida, H. 2003. The spider family Theridiidae (Arachnida: Araneae) from Japan. *Arachnol. Soc. Japan*, : 1-224.
- 21) Zabka, M. 1997. Salticidae: PajakiSkaczace (Arachnida: Araneae). *Fauna Polski*, 19:1-188.
- 22) Nyffeler, M. and Benz, G., 1987. Spiders in natural pest control: a review 1. *Journal of Applied Entomology*, 103(1-5), pp.321-339.
- 23) Nyffeler, M. and Benz, G., 1981. Field studies on the feeding ecology of spiders: observations in the region of Zurich (Switzerland). *Anzeiger für Schädlingkunde, Pflanzenschutz, Umweltschutz*, 54, pp.33-39.
- 24) Platnick, N.I., 2019. The guardstone spiders of the Phrurotimpuspalustris group (Araneae, Phrurolithidae). *American Museum Novitates*, 2019(3944), pp.1-32.
- 25) Farooq, M., Sheikh, S.A., Miano, T.F. and Memon, N., 2018. Physicochemical characteristics of value added banana products. *J. Agric. Res*, 56(4), pp.265-269.
- 26) Nabi, G., Talpur, B.A., Jarwar, I.A. and Sial, M., 2020. Exploration of Banana Based Cropping System in District Khairpur Sindh Pakistan.
- 27) Khaskheli, A.J., Ali, M., Shah, S.Z.H., Memon, Z.F., Awan, S., Khaskheli, M.I., Khaskheli, M.A., Magsi, B., Qambrani, Z. and Khaskheli, A.A., 2021. Initiation, proliferation, and improvement of a micropropagation system for mass clonal production of banana through shoot-tip culture. *Journal of Plant Biotechnology*, 48(2), pp.86-92.